

Developing Innovative Processes for Microalgae-Based Sustainable Aviation Fuels SusAlgaeFuel Project Launched in Dublin, Ireland

Dublin, Ireland – The SusAlgaeFuel project officially launched with a kick-off meeting held at University College Dublin (UCD). Dr. Ronald Halim, the project coordinator, hosted the consortium of partners at UCD's facilities. The event was inaugurated by Prof. Kate Robson, UCD Vice President of Research, Innovation and Impact, who welcomed the attendees during the official launch ceremony.

Co-funded by the European Union, the SusAlgaeFuel project focuses on advancing innovative processes for producing cost-competitive and sustainable aviation fuel from microalgae. This initiative combines approaches such as direct carbon capture, nutrient recovery, and next-generation purification technologies.

Air travel remains a significant contributor to greenhouse gas emissions, and algae-based biofuels present a promising solution to reduce the aviation sector's environmental footprint. Microalgae have the potential to generate large amounts of lipids, which can be converted into bio-kerosene. Compared to conventional jet fuels, algae-based fuels could reduce CO₂ emissions by up to 70%.

Ultimately, the goal of SusAlgaeFuel is *“to cultivate microalgae using digestate and CO₂ emissions from anaerobic digestion and to convert this microalgal biomass into sustainable aviation fuel at a scalable level”*, emphasizes Halim in his speech at the launch.

Prof. Robson also highlighted the significance of UCD's role in coordinating this high-impact project, stating: *“SusAlgaeFuel brings together leading technology providers in microalgal cultivation and AI-driven sensor technology, alongside experts in biomass processing and aviation fuel synthesis. This collaboration reflects our shared commitment to developing climate-friendly biofuels and will result in the construction of a pilot-scale microalgal facility at Ireland's largest biomethane producer, BIA Energy.”*

The SusAlgaeFuel project started in May 2024 and will run for 48 months. It involves nine partner institutions from five European countries, all working towards the shared vision of making aviation more sustainable. The European Union is providing co-funding for the project, with a contribution of up to €3.47 million.

For further updates and information on SusAlgaeFuel, visit the project website at www.susalgaefuel.eu, or follow the project on LinkedIn and Bluesky.

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Picture: SusAlgaeFuel consortium members met on 01 and 02 October 2024 in Dublin, to officially kickstart the project. Picture Source: ESCI, free for usage.

Ronald Halim and Kate Robson (both University College Dublin) during the official launch of SusAlgaeFuel. Picture Source: UCD, free for usage